

MONITORING STRESS IN ARUGULA (*Eruca sativa*) USING A PORTABLE MULTISPECTRAL DEVICE

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Abstract

One of the factors that most severely limits plant production is a rise in salinized soil, which is brought on by a combination of pollution and contemporary farming methods. Arugula (*Eruca sativa*), a green leafy vegetable belonging to the Brassicaceae family, is rich in proteins, fibers, and vitamins A, C, and K. Arugula is a powerful antioxidant and anti-inflammatory because of its biochemical composition. Arugula plants were subjected to 0 mM NaCl (C), 40 mM NaCl (T2), and 80 mM NaCl (T3) solutions for 60 days throughout the 2024 growing season to determine the impact of soil salinity. Indoor growing conditions were provided for the plants in pots. Each treatment was run through three replicates. Temperature was used to estimate the early stress response of the arugula plants. The leaf's progressive reduction in temperature when exposed to salt solution is an indication of a stress reaction. Plant spectral reflectance was measured using the handheld multispectral sensor Plant-O-Meter. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) were the two vegetational indices (VI) that were utilized to evaluate the plant response. Significant variations between treatments for both calculated indices are revealed by the calculation of f-ratio values. When ANOVA is used for multiple comparison analysis testing, the NDVI values of T1 and T3, as well as T2 and T3, differ significantly. There are notable variations in EVI values between T1 and T2, as well as T1 and T3 treatments. These findings suggest the possible use of remote sensing tools to forecast stress in arugula by utilizing NDVI and EVI.

Key words: *arugula, NDVI, EVI, salinization, leaf temperature.*

Introduction

In contemporary agriculture, there is a rising gap between the expanding need for food and the corresponding escalating land degradation. Projections of human population show steady growth, while soil degradation, of which soil salinization is a major issue, will continue to trend negatively. Contemporary agriculture production, especially irrigation and fertilization management, are one of the major factors which lead to soil salinization. Although anthropogenic influence has a remarkable effect, there are other elements that contribute to soil degradation and subsequent salinization. Salinization is predicted to get worse due to climate change, which will cause more frequent and severe droughts as well as sea level rise (Singh, 2021, Nogacz et al., 2022).

Optimization of agricultural production under salinization is necessary and can be properly implemented if the stress is detected in initial phase and mechanism of action of salt stress on plant as well as its reaction is known. According to recent studies (Nogacz et al., 2022, Vellinga et al., 2021), salinity interferes with nitrogen intake, causing growth inhibition. As a consequence, plant reproduction is halted and normal plant development and productivity are inhibited. Additionally, oxygen exchange is altered during stress. Plants eventually die when the concentration of certain ions, especially chloride, rises because of their toxicity.

Arugula (*Eruca sativa*), also referred to as rocket, is a green leafy vegetable from the Brassicaceae family. Originating in the Mediterranean area, it is a very well-liked salad ingredient (Garg & Sharma, 2014). This is supported by the fact that raw arugula has been used in salads in Italy since the Roman era. Usually, the species grows on arid, rugged soil. Traditionally, the plant was gathered from the wild or planted in household gardens alongside other herbs like basil and parsley. Nowadays, arugula is grown commercially in many locations all over the world. Apart from the leaves, edible parts include the blooms, immature seed pods, and mature seeds. Currently, thanks to its content, arugula is used as a garnish for mixed salads, where it lends a pleasant sharpness (Gulfraz et al., 2011, Komerowski et al., 2023).

With only a small quantity of fat, raw arugula is rich in proteins, vitamins (A, C, and K), and fibers. It is an abundant source of vitamin folate, while magnesium, calcium, manganese, and vitamin C. Next to the role in nutrition, arugula is recognized as a valuable source in medicine and pharmaceutical industry. When used as medicine, the arugula stimulates hair growth and has antibacterial, antidiabetic, antihypertensive, antiplatelet, and antioxidant properties (Gulfraz et al., 2011, Greg and Sharma, 2014).

Vegetation indices (VIs) derived from remote sensing of canopies are straightforward and effective algorithms for quantitative and qualitative assessments of vegetation cover, plant vigor, growth dynamics, and other relevant parameters. More than one hundred vegetation indices have been derived from multispectral imagery (Xue and Su, 2017). These indices facilitate the identification of nutrient deficiencies, water stress, extreme temperatures, soil coverage, diagnosis of biological parameters, and yield estimation (Andrade et al., 2022).

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is one of the earliest and most widely used indices for vegetation assessment due to its simplicity and compatibility with any multispectral sensor equipped with visible and near-IR bands (Huang et al., 2021). Mathematically, NDVI is expressed as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

However, the interaction between soil and atmosphere can complicate the interpretation of NDVI, as reducing the influence of one can amplify the effects of the other. To address this issue, a feedback mechanism was introduced through the development of the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), which simultaneously corrects for both soil and atmospheric effects (Xue and Su, 2017). The EVI is expressed as follows:

$$EVI = 2.5 \left(\frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + 2.4RED + 1} \right)$$

The aim of this study was to investigate the early salt stress-induced response in arugula. We summarized the effect of salinization through NDVI and EVI analysis using the portable multispectral optical device Plant-O-Meter, which integrates a multispectral light source consisting of wavelengths at 850, 630, 535, and 465 nm, enabling simultaneous illumination of the entire plant (Kitić et al., 2019).

Material and Methods

The experiment represented growing arugula plants from seeds in indoor conditions in Novi Sad, Serbia (45.2396° N, 19.8227° E). At the beginning of February 2024, the arugula seeds were planted in a commercial substrate. Once the seedlings reached the height of 5 cm, they were transplanted into test pots. The seedlings were irrigated by ponding according to their specific needs until they had grown to an average height of 10 to 15 cm and had become adapted to the conditions. Following the establishment of healthy plant conditions and consistent development, solutions with varying NaCl concentrations were applied to the plants to subject them to saline stress. Treatments were applied regularly; there was an

irrigation interval of three days, while the concentrations of the saline solution were 0 (T1), 40 (T2) and 80 (T3) mM NaCl. After sixty days of exposure to salt stress, vegetation indices NDVI and EVI were evaluated using a multispectral optical device Plant-O-Meter. An infrared thermometer was used to measure the leaf's temperature simultaneously.

All statistical tests were carried out using the Statistical Analysis System Statistica 6.1 version. An overall difference between sample means were tested by one-way ANOVA (for $P < 0.05$). whether Tukey's HSD test was used to determine significance between the pairs of treatments.

Results and Discussion

This study investigated how different treatments affected NDVI values in arugula under early salt stress conditions. Analysis of variance revealed significant variations among treatments ($F = 18.47109$, $p < 0.05$, Table 1). Further pairwise comparisons showed that NDVI values did not significantly differ between treatments T2 and T2 ($Q = 0,022$, Table 2), suggesting similar responses. In contrast, significant differences were observed between T1 and T2 ($Q = 0.66$), as well as T1 and T3 ($Q=0,64$), indicating distinct effects of treatment T3 on vegetation indices. These results underscore NDVI's sensitivity as an indicator of salt-induced stress in arugula, providing valuable insights into treatment-specific physiological responses. Similar results were obtained in Aldakheel (2011) study, where lower NDVI values may correspond to high electrical conductivity of the soils, suggesting that soil salinity impacts vegetation health, similar to the treatment-induced variations in NDVI observed in our study. Indices based on chlorophyll absorption bands and the NIR region, such as NDVI, had a strong relation with soil salinity because these indices are related to the growth of plants, biomass, leaf area and chlorophyll content (Zhang et al., 2011).

Table 1. Summary of one-way analysis of variance performed on parameters NDVI, EVI, and leaf temperature of basil subjected to 0 (T1), 40 (T2) and 80 (T3) mM NaCl solutions ($P < 0.05$)

Evaluated parameters	One-way ANOVA testing (df=2)	
	F- statistics	p-value
NDVI	18.471	1.85E-07
EVI	34.124	8.13E-10
Leaf temperature	3.985	0.02212

Similarly, the study explored the response of Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) values in arugula under various treatments subjected to early salt stress. Analysis of variance revealed significant differences among treatments ($F = 34.124$, $p < 0.05$, Table 1), highlighting diverse effects on EVI across experimental conditions. Pairwise comparisons (Table 2) revealed that treatment T1 exhibited significantly higher EVI values compared to both T2 (mean difference = 0.064, $p < 0.05$) and T3 (mean difference = 0.045, $p < 0.05$), indicating a heightened response to salt stress. Conversely, no significant difference was found between T2 and T3 (mean difference = 0.019), suggesting similar EVI responses under these treatments. These findings underscore EVI's sensitivity in detecting early physiological changes induced by salt stress in arugula, emphasizing its utility in evaluating treatment-specific plant responses in controlled agricultural environments. Lobell et al. (2010) concluded that EVI is a more reliable measure of vegetation condition and, consequently, salinity, compared to NDVI.

Table 2. Difference between means of treatments 0 (T1), 40 (T2) and 80 (T3) mM NaCl tested by multiple comparison test (Tukey HSD test, $P < 0.05$).

Pair	NDVI		EVI		Leaf temperature	
	Q	p-value	Q	p-value	Q	p-value
T1-T2	0,66	1.52E-07	0.064	8.13E-10	0.66	0.0451
T1-T3	0,64	0.0002126	0.045	1.45E-09	0.67	0.0400
T2-T3	0.022	0.1706	0.019	0.9666	0.01	0.9986

This study analyzed temperature variation among treatments. A total of 90 observations were distributed across three treatments. Mean temperatures were 22.1°C (T1), 21.8°C (T 2), and 21.5°C (T3), with corresponding standard deviations of 0.8909, 0.9852, and 0.7018°C, respectively. Analysis of variance revealed a sum of squares (SS) between treatments of 3.926 with 2 degrees of freedom (df), resulting in a mean square (MS) of 1.963 and an F-ratio of 2.60934 (Table 1). The associated p-value was 0.079335, indicating a trend towards significance at the $p < 0.05$ level. These results suggest potential treatment effects on temperature variation. Tian et al. (2020) concluded in their study that plants subjected to salt stress exhibited significantly higher leaf temperatures compared to the control group. These findings underscore the importance of monitoring leaf temperature as an indicator of plant responses to stressful conditions.

Conclusions

The arugula's early stress response was estimated using temperature. When a leaf is exposed to salt solution, its temperature gradually drops, which is a sign of a stress reaction. Plant-O-Meter, a portable multispectral sensor, was used to detect the spectral reflectance of plants. The two vegetational indices (VI) that were used to assess the plant response were the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). The F-ratio values computation reveals significant differences between treatments for both derived indices. The ANOVA multiple comparison analysis highlighted significant difference in the NDVI values of T1 and T3, as well as T2 and T3. EVI values differ significantly between T1 and T2, as well as between T1 and T3 treatments. These results imply that NDVI and EVI could be used as remote sensing metrics to predict stress in arugula.

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